

Structural Control of Photoconductivity in a Flexible Titanium-Organic Framework

Clara Chinchilla-Garzón, Marta Galbiati, Alechania Misturini, Pol Gimeno-Fonquernie, Neyvis Almora-Barrios, Natalia M. Padial and Carlos Martí-Gastaldo**

Dedicated to Omar Yaghi on his 60th birthday.

C. Chinchilla-Garzón, M. Galbiati, A. Misturini, P. Gimeno-Fonquernie, N. Almora-Barrios, N. M. Padial, C. Martí-Gastaldo
Instituto de Ciencia Molecular (ICMol). Universitat de València, Catedrático José Beltrán-2, 46980, Paterna, Spain.
E-mail: natalia.munoz@uv.es, carlos.marti@uv.es

Keywords: framework flexibility, titanium MOF, photoconductivity, through-space transport

The soft nature of Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) sets them apart from other non-synthetic porous materials. Their flexibility allows the framework components to rearrange in response to environmental changes, leading to different states and properties. Our work extends this concept to titanium frameworks, demonstrating control over charge transport in porous molecular crystals. MUV-35 is a two-fold catenated framework composed of heterometallic TiMn_2 trimers and electron donor 4,4',4''-(benzo[1,2-*b*:3,4-*b'*:5,6-*b''*]trithiophene-2,5,8-triyl)tribenzoic acid (H_3BTTTB) linkers, forming a rare sit-c net topology that can fold to reduce its volume by about 40% through a single-crystal transformation controlled by linker conformation in open, intermediate, and closed states. This process, driven by a free energy difference of nearly $300 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, originates from the formation of a continuous network of non-covalent interactions that force the spontaneous loss of the solvent in the pores of the framework to establish charge transport pathways that afford photocurrents of $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ under visible light for an ON/OFF ratio (ΔR) of four orders of magnitude. This photoconductivity rivals the best conductivity values described for through-transport conductive MOFs while maintaining a porosity of nearly $1.000 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$.

1. Introduction

Reticular chemistry has boosted the design of an increasingly high number of Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) or Porous Coordination Polymers (PCPs) with unlimited chemical compositions, structures and sizeable porosities.^[1,2] The use of geometrical design concepts^[3,4] and the development of post-synthetic methodologies^[5] for fine tuning of MOF surface chemistry are arguably responsible for the rapid growth of the field and its increasing importance in modern catalysis, storage and separation technologies.^[6-10] Compared to the rigid porosity of traditional sorbents such as zeolites or mesoporous silica, MOFs can display a unique framework flexibility and are capable of adjusting their structure to the uptake/removal of guest molecules or external stimuli without appreciable loss of crystallinity.^[11] These “soft” crystals combine the regularity of inorganic materials with the softness of organic polymers for distinctive properties like breathing,^[12] gating^[13] or negative gas adsorption,^[14] all relevant to applications as gas adsorption/storage,^[15-17] sensing^[18,19] or drug delivery.^[20] All these examples are solid proof of the possibilities offered by the design of porous materials with flexible responses. However, exploiting this phenomenon to gain control over the charge transport in MOFs/PCPs remains unexplored. Over the last decade, tremendous progress has been made in

improving the electrical conductivity of MOFs, which have recently reached metallic conductivities near $1000 \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$.^[21] This trend has also been reinforced by the availability of crystals and experimental structural models that are compatible with the calculation of periodic electronic structures.^[22–25] Among the different routes to achieve charge transport in porous frameworks, we hypothesized that the through-space pathway was more adequate for integrating conductivity and framework flexibility. This type of conductive MOFs involves adapting organic blocks prone to oxidize and form stable radical cations such as tetrathiofulvalene (TTF),^[26] naphthalenediimide (NDI),^[27] or hexaazaphenalene (HAP),^[28] to framework formation by functionalization with benzoate or pyridyl units. Among them, tetrathiofulvalene tetrabenzoate (TTFTB) is the prevailing linker used in the assembly of conductive MOFs based on transition metal ions ($M^{2+} = \text{Cd}, \text{Mn}, \text{Co}, \text{Zn}$)^[29,30] and lanthanides ($\text{Ln}^{3+} = \text{La}, \text{Gd}, \text{Tb}, \text{Dy}, \text{Ho}, \text{Er}, \text{Yb}, \text{Lu}$).^[31–34] We argued that the use of alternative linkers with lower connectivity and secondary building units (SBUs) not restricted to infinite chains would be more adequate to prove our concept. As summarized in **Figure 1**, the formation of more open frameworks in which the structural flexibility of the organic connector can be altered in response to the removal of solvent molecules might lead to varying packing modes.^[35] The corresponding change of the spatial separation between π - π stacked organic units enables an extended path for charge delocalization. If these electron donor units were also combined with titanium-oxo clusters, acting as electron acceptors for the generation of titanium (III) sites upon charge transfer, this structural change might be accompanied by electrical conductivity under light irradiation, as result of the transport of photogenerated charge-separated states.

We demonstrate this concept with MUV-35 (MUV = Materials of the University of València). This double interpenetrated framework displays a spontaneous folding upon solvent loss orchestrated by linker conformational changes to adopt a closed state that maximizes the organization and density of organic donors to afford photoconductivity under visible light.

Figure 1. Proposed structural control of photoconductivity in titanium frameworks. The structural response of a titanium framework to solvent (S) removal leads to a reorganization in the packing of organic donors to form a through-space transport pathway that enables photoconductivity upon the generation of charge-separated states.

2. Results and discussion

MUV-35: spontaneous folding upon solvent loss.

Benzo-tris-thiophene displays good light absorption, electron-donor character, and ability to generate π -extended systems with good charge mobility.^[36] It is similar to TTF from an electronic point of view, but its internal symmetry makes it compatible with the design of alternative MOF topologies based on tri-connected organic nodes. We recently reported MUV-30, a microporous framework built from the interconnection of benzo[1,2-b:3,4-b':5,6-b'']trithiophene-2,5,8-tricarboxylic acid (H_3BTT) and 8-

connected (8-c) $[\text{Ti}_2\text{Ca}_2(\mu_2\text{-O})_2(\text{RCO}_2)_8]$ SBUs.^[37] Unfortunately, the relative orientation and spatial separation of BTT units in this framework is far from adequate to enable charge hopping. To facilitate the formation of more open frameworks that could facilitate the packing of BTT units, we chose to synthesize an elongated version by Suzuki cross-coupling of benzoate units with the brominated BTT, followed by a saponification reaction to form 4,4',4''-(benzo[1,2-*b*:3,4-*b'*:5,6-*b''*']trithiophene-2,5,8-triyl)tribenzoic acid (H_3BTTTB). Synthetic details and the corresponding characterization are described in **Supplementary Section S2**. MUV-35 was synthesized in 5 mL PTFE bottles by the reaction of titanium (IV) isopropoxide (32.5 μmol) with a mixture of manganese (II) chloride (20.0 μmol), acetic acid (200 μL) and H_3BTTTB (24.0 μmol) in 3 mL of *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) at 115°C for 48 h. After screening several synthetic variables as temperature, reaction time, solvent, modulator and linker concentrations, and different titanium precursors, we found these conditions optimal to grow single crystals with prismatic morphology and size near to 100 μm (**Figure 2a**).

Figure 2. Structure of MUV-35. a) Microscope images of as-made crystals used for crystallographic analysis. b) Structure of the 6-c trigonal prismatic TiMn_2 clusters and the 3-c BTTTB linkers, highlighting their internal geometry. c) Staggered π - π stacking of BTTTB linkers from catenated nets (red and blue) showing a parallel displaced orientation. d) Doubly interpenetrated structure of MUV-35 along the b-axis showing the presence of 1D lozenge-shaped channels. e) N_2 adsorption isotherms at 77 K and experimental PSD plot (NLDFT model, regularization = 0.1). f) Simulated and experimental diffraction patterns of MUV-35 under different conditions anticipating the sensitivity of the structure to framework-guest interaction.

MUV-35 crystallizes in the monoclinic $I2/m$ space group and it is built from the interlinking of 6-c trigonal prismatic $[\text{TiMn}_2(\mu_3\text{-O})(\text{X})_3(\text{RCO}_2)_6]$ ($\text{X} = \text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{DMF}$) trimers and 3-c BTTTB triangular linkers (**Figure 2b**). Although the formation of heterometallic $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{M}_2^{\text{II}}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Mg}, \text{Co}, \text{Ni}$) trimers is dominant under similar synthetic conditions, as exemplified by the MUV-101 and 301 families,^[37-39] the internal geometry of this cluster is significantly distorted and displays closer angles between the carboxylates for a compressed prism in MUV-35. This is accompanied by the breakage of carboxylates coplanarity in BTTTB, which does not correspond to a regular flat triangle (180°) and takes on a concave shape instead. These deviations from ideality are generated by the presence of non-covalent π -interactions between BTT units, which form a staggered stacking with parallel displaced orientation and an interplanar distance of 3.55 Å (**Figure 2c**). Although the default structure for these building blocks is the *moo* (or zeolitic *mtn*) topology, based on its high prevalence for M^{III} trimers or heterometallic $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{M}_2^{\text{II}}$ analogues, the stacking of BTT dimers seems responsible for the generation of a geometry mismatch^[40] that drives instead the formation of a two-fold interpenetrated sit-c net (**Figure 2d**). This topology is quite elusive, and to our understanding the only example listed in the RCSR database is MOF-39, described in 2001 by Yaghi and co-workers.^[41] The solvent accessible volume in the structure of MUV-35 occupies 56.1% of the crystallographic cell and results from the intersection of 1D lozenge-shaped channels with a pore opening diameter of approximately 13 Å along the b-axis, with narrower apertures along a. Regarding the distribution of metals in the TiMn_2 cluster, the presence of two types of axial groups, DMF and water solvent molecules, coordinated respectively to the Mn(II) and Ti(IV) sites, allows to crystallographically discriminate both types of metals whose relative proportion fits well with the 2:1 ratio and its homogeneous distribution revealed by SEM-Energy-dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX) and ICP-MS (**Supplementary Section S.3.1**). The X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) spectrum of MUV-35 also confirms the presence of these metals in Mn^{2+} and Ti^{4+} oxidation states.

To confirm the open structure of MUV-35, we activated the material at 120 °C under dynamic vacuum for 12 h before collecting the N_2 adsorption isotherm at 77 K. **Figure 2e** shows a type-I isotherm characteristic of a microporous material, with a surface area of $930 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ that corresponds to a narrow pore size distribution (PSD) that agrees with the presence of a micropore diameter centered at 10 Å. The values in question are considerably lower in both surface area and pore size than those estimated by Poreblazer, $1,490 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and 12 Å, by using the crystallographic structure of MUV-35. The thermogravimetric analysis indicates a thermal stability under an air flow superior to 380 °C that discards the framework decomposition as result of the thermal treatment (**Figure S6**). This deviation could be indicative instead of a partial collapse of the porous structure. We also observed a color change in the crystals from yellowish orange to brown, which could be associated to a structural change or caused by local changes in the coordination environment of Mn(II) sites upon removal of the axially coordinated solvent molecules. It is worth noting that the titanium framework COK-69 displays a flexible response for framework folding upon solvent loss,^[42] and other Ti-MOFs as USTC-700^[43] or the FIR series^[44] also reveal local changes in conformation or coordination modes although without significant impact on the overall structure.

To clarify this further, we collected the powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns of as-made MUV-35 crystals soaked in DMF (solvent), left to dry in open air (dry), and left to dry in open air after exchanged with acetone (dry/acetone). **Figure 2f** shows that only the crystals immersed in DMF fit well to the simulated pattern for the MUV-35 structure, while both acetone exchanged and evacuated crystals display a significant structural change, which seems to correspond to a structural compression upon removal of DMF, according to the shift of the more intense diffraction line at higher angular values.

Figure 3. Framework folding in MUV-35. a) From left to right: open (o), intermediate (i) and closed (c) structures of MUV-35 viewed along the b-axis. The loss of solvent induces an expansion of the c-axis concomitant to a compression of the ab plane that reduces the cell volume in near to 37%. b) Folding upon spontaneous solvent loss is controlled by a concerted motion based on the closure of the torsion angles of the benzoate arms in the cluster (top) that enables a change in the conformation of the BTTTB linker to form an alternative packing arrangement with shorter inter-BTT distances (bottom). c) Sequence of images taken for a freshly synthesised MUV-35 crystal soaked in DMF that show the spontaneous changes of the crystal with time at room temperature.

To validate this hypothesis, we redetermined the structure of MUV-35 by single crystal experiments on the Synchrotron ALBA (BL13-XALOC) under different conditions. To avoid the structural transformation at room temperature, a freshly picked crystal was mounted in a MicroMount™ followed by insertion into a thin-walled polyethylene terephthalate (PET) capillary filled with methanol. As shown in **Figure 3a**, the presence of the solvent permits capturing a more open structure that we will refer to as MUV-

35-open (o). In turn, data collection from crystals that were not flash-cooled in liquid nitrogen revealed the formation of MUV-35-closed (c) as result of the folding of the framework. Together with the structure already described for as-made crystals filled with DMF that correspond to an intermediate (i) folding state, the data confirm that MUV-35 undergoes an isomorphic $o \rightarrow i \rightarrow c$ folding upon solvent loss by uniaxial compression of the monoclinic cell along the b-axis. Compared to MUV-35-o, the length of the a-axis is compressed by about $\Delta a = 11.3 \text{ \AA}$, while the c-axis is elongated up to 4.5 \AA , resulting in a compression of the cell volume of near to 37% of the initial value (**Figure 3a**). This change does not modify the framework connectivity, which maintains the same porous structure of intersected lozenge-shaped channels but reduces their internal diameter to about 8 \AA , » 33% narrower than in the open structure for an expected surface area of $1.150 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ that agrees better with the experimental adsorption in **Figure 2e**, pointing to the folding of the framework during activation.

MUV-35 undergoes a structural transition that triggers a displacement of the atoms in the framework upon guest desorption for a $\Delta V \approx 0$ change of the unit cell.^[45,46] Compared to archetypical flexible frameworks as the breathing 'wine-rack' MIL-53^[47] and MIL-88^[48] families, in which the as-synthesized structures are only slightly compressed $\Delta V < 5\%$ by thermal treatment (dry), the folding of MUV-35 is spontaneous and the desorption of DMF proceeds without thermal heating or vacuum. Compared to the closed structures of MIL-53 and MIL-88 that can be swelled reaching $\Delta V > 250\%$ as a function of the length of the linker and host-guest interactions, the folding in MUV-35 is irreversible and anticipates a strong stabilization of the folded state that makes it insensitive to framework-guest interactions.

Breathing in MIL-88 is dominated by a kneecap mechanism,^[48] in which the carboxylate groups act as hinges, allowing the free rotation of both the M_3 trimers and the aromatic ring in the linker. The folding mechanism in MUV-35 is different as result of its different topology and connectivity. It also remains rigid along the direction of the channels but undergoes a compression in the ac plane, triggered by a spontaneous solvent loss that is controlled by a change in the torsion angles of the benzoate units around the central BTT core, which remain flat in both states (**Figure 3b**). In the open structure, all carboxylate groups are in the same plane of the aromatic molecule (syn disposition), adopting a bent conformation. The progressive twisting of one of the three benzoate arms by up to » 19° with respect to the BTT unit forces a change in the geometry of the linker, that adopts an anti-disposition to enable the folding of the framework and modify the distances separating the $TiMn_2$ trimers along the a ($\Delta d = -11.03 \text{ \AA}$) and c ($+4.51 \text{ \AA}$) axes. Catenation plays a fundamental role in the folding of MUV-35. While in the case of MIL-88 the stabilization by interactions with the guest incorporated into the pore of the dry phase is what triggers the cell expansion, in MUV-35 the loss of DMF (b.p. $165 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) seems to occur spontaneously to induce a cell compression. This allows an alternative stacking of BTT units along the a-axis, which display the same staggered arrangement but shorter distances between planes of 3.44 and 3.13 \AA for stronger non-covalent interactions that stabilize the folded state.

To confirm the spontaneity of this process, we analyzed with an optical microscope the evolution in size and morphology of freshly made MUV-35 crystals synthesized and soaked in DMF and exposed to the environment for 10 minutes at room temperature. **Figure 3c** shows how the crystals that are intact in an initial stage give way after a few minutes to the appearance of streaks along its axes, followed in a later stage by a compression and twisting of the crystal that we associate to the folding of the framework. The reader is referred to **Supplementary Movie S1** for a dynamic overview of this process.

Theoretical description of the structural flexibility of MUV-35.

As described in detail in **Supplementary Section S5.1**, in a first approximation we described computationally the different structures of solvent-free MUV-35 with the pGFN-FF model.^[49] The

optimized structures at constant volume show minimal deviations from the crystallographic data. A preliminary analysis of the empty frameworks agrees well with the spontaneous open to close or large to narrow pore (lp→np) transformation observed experimentally, with a Helmholtz free energy difference (ΔF) between both states of $-303.6 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ per unit cell at 300 K. In magnitude, this free energy difference is considerably larger when compared with other flexible MOFs from the literature. For instance, this same phase transition involves 40 or 60 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ in average depending on the guest for COMOC-2(V),^[50] an isostructural vanadium analogue of MIL-47. The gate opening of DUT-8(Ni)^[51] or MIL-53(Al)^[52] in presence of solvent molecules have a $\Delta F_{np\rightarrow lp}$ of 110 or 20 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively, suggesting a significant energetic gain from the guest uptake is necessary to overcome the stability of the closed phase

Figure 4. Computational analysis of the structural flexibility in MUV-35. a) Representative configurations of the folding of MUV-35 upon guest loss. These geometries correspond to the last configuration of the MD simulations run during 500 ps, containing 90, 85, 75, 55 and 35 DMF molecules. b) Average lattice parameters *a*, *b* and *c* sampled during the MD simulations. The corresponding experimental values are highlighted with coloured circles. c) Evolution of the average interframework and framework-guest interaction energies with the compression of the cell volume, calculated from all the configurations sampled during the MD simulations.

and trigger the opening of the structure. Also, a series of phase transformations in different MOF structures have been reported with $|\Delta F|$ in a range of 2-6 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.^[53-55]

Compared to these examples, the folding of MUV-35 is mostly enthalpically driven and dominated by non-covalent interactions (NCI), with only a small entropic contribution of $\Delta S_{o\rightarrow c} = -1.5 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$. This is intrinsically different to the flexible response of other frameworks for which a closer energy balance between enthalpic and entropic contributions is estimated. For example, the $np\rightarrow lp$ opening in MIL-53(Al) for which the calculated ΔH and ΔS values of 74 $\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ and 15 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ ^[56] lead to a more complex free energy landscape where phase transitions that can be navigated by small changes in energy triggered by temperature, guest uptake or other external stimuli.^[57-59] As detailed in the **Supplementary Section S.5.2**, we next used the NCI method^[60] to evaluate the different inter-framework interactions between the open

and closed states of MUV-35 in the form of gradient isosurfaces to represent the spatial rearrangement of the π -electronic density upon structural transformation (**Figure S18a**). The small red surfaces in the center of the rings correspond to repulsive steric effects, whereas those colored in green correspond to the presence of weak van der Waals interactions. Compared to MUV-35-o that features isolated green surfaces from π - π -interactions between BTTTB linkers from catenated nets, the folding of the frameworks induces the onset of additional attractive stacking interactions in MUV-35-c. A comparison of the reduced-density gradient (RDG) plots for both frameworks (**Figure S18b**) shows MUV-35-c peaks slightly shifted toward larger density ($|\rho|$) values, indicating a small strengthening of the π - π -interactions^[61] upon closing. Although MUV-35 structural transition is not associated to significant changes in the electronic density, its spatial reorganization favors the establishment of a continuous array of through-space interactions along the a-axis.

We also analyzed the folding of solvated MUV-35 with Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations upon progressive loss of DMF guest molecules (**Supplementary Section S.6.3**). **Figure 4a** shows five representative frames of the simulations with pore occupation of 90, 85, 75, 55 and 35 DMF molecules, that include the three configurations closest to the experimental o, i, and c and two states between them. For the complete folding trajectory please check **Figure S19** and **Supplementary Movie S2**. As shown in **Figure 4b**, our simulation not only provides a good agreement between the simulated lengths of the lattice and the corresponding crystallographic structures, but also reproduces the uniaxial expansion and compression upon solvent loss of the c and a-axis while leaving the b-axis almost intact. The average interaction energies were calculated from different configurations sampled during the MD simulations to evaluate the progressive changes in the framework-guest solvent adsorption energy normalized to the number of guest molecules in the cell ($\overline{\Delta E^{ads}}$) for each configuration, and the inter-framework interactions between catenated nets (ΔE^{int}), both associated to the folding of MUV-35. As anticipated by the analysis of the empty frameworks, **Figure 4c** confirms that the o \rightarrow c transition is enthalpically driven, for a massive stabilization of $-341.8 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ by dispersive interframework π - π interactions with only a minor effect of framework-guest interactions.

For the sake of comparison with the literature, we also removed the guest molecules and computed the single-point energy difference between the open and closed frameworks (ΔE_F , **Supplementary Section S.5.4**). The value of $\Delta E_F = -295.6 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ results from the combination of the stabilizing ΔE^{int} interactions already described, and a deformation energy (ΔE^{def}) of $23.15 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ that penalizes the framework transformation but is easily counterbalanced by the energy gain resulting from the folding of the framework for near to a 38% compression of the cell volume. This value of ΔE_F confirms a stabilization of the closed framework and a preference for folding in MUV-35 far superior to those described for other flexible MOFs as the 8-folded interpenetrated JUK-8,^[62] with $\Delta E_F = -183.3 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for a change in cell volume of approximately 24% controlled by non-covalent interactions, DUT-8(M) between -50 and $-104 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ depending on the metal of choice,^[57] the H-bond controlled folding of the peptide-based framework Zn(GlySer)₂ with $-84.2 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$,^[63] or the contraction of MIL-53(Al) that involves ΔE_F values between -5.0 or $-10.5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ depending on the DFT method employed.^[64]

These analyses confirm the thermodynamic preference of MUV-35 for spontaneous folding anticipated by our experimental results. Despite the high boiling point of DMF, the enormous energy gain resulting from the formation of a network of enhanced π - π interactions in MUV-35-c is sufficient to expel solvent molecules at environmental conditions. In contrast to other flexible systems, where the energy differences between the open and closed states are of comparable magnitude to the framework-guest interactions, allowing an interconversion between the two states depending on the adsorbate or other

external stimuli, the folding in the catenated structure of MUV-35 is dominated by inter-framework interactions that lead to a thermodynamic minimum nondependent on framework-adsorbate interactions that cannot be reversed under comparable conditions.

Photoinduced conductivity in MUV-35-c

As discussed in the introduction, the folding of MUV-35 into a thermodynamically stable, closed structure combining photoreducible titanium nodes with a reinforced network of through-space transport pathways that enables a separation between BTT units with distances compatible with electronic hopping between π -stacked units could endow this material with photoconductivity depending on its ability to generate and transport charge carriers upon irradiation.

We collected the UV-Vis solid spectrum of MUV-35 crystals using an integrating sphere. The crystals darken from yellow (open) to darker brown (closed) as result of the spontaneous solvent desorption and subsequent structural change. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of MUV-35-c is dominated by a broad absorption band extending from the mid-visible to the UV, with a maximum centered at about 450 nm (Supplementary Section S.6.1). This corresponds to an optical band gap of 2.3 eV as estimated by a linear fit of the Tauc plot, that would be compatible with visible light photoexcitation. Light absorption in titanium MOFs is often dominated by photoexcitation of the organic ligand for the formation of a charge separation state that can result in a linker-to-metal charge transfer for the photogeneration of Ti^{3+} centers. To confirm this possibility, we recorded the EPR spectrum of an acetonitrile suspension of MUV-35-c in the dark and after irradiation with UV light (Kessil PR160L-370 nm lamp). As shown in Figure S23, no differences are observed between the two spectra that are dominated by the paramagnetic signal of the octahedral Mn^{2+} sites ($S = 5/2$) with a g -value of 2.15.

Figure 5. Electronic structure and photoconductivity in MUV-35-c. a) Electronic DOS spectra aligned relative to the vacuum level of MUV-35-c. The grey background area is the HOCO and LUCO. b) Optical microscope image of a MUV-35-c crystal contacted with silver paint for electrical transport measurements. c) I-V transport curve measured in the crystal in dark and when illuminated with blue light (Kessil PR160L-440 nm lamp). A linear representation of both curves is displayed in Figure S27. d) Consecutive ON-OFF photocurrent cycles when sample irradiated with 440 nm light source. e) Photocurrent measured in the crystal when illuminated with lights of different wavelengths for an applied voltage $V=10$ V. Dotted line is a guide to the eye.

As in MUV-10(Mn),^[65] also formed by Ti_2Mn_2 heterometallic clusters, this does not allow to identify the formation of Ti^{3+} species ($S = 1/2$) and their characteristic resonance below $g = 2.0$. For a better understanding of the conduction pathways in the framework we calculated the electronic structures and density of states (DOS) diagram of MUV-35-c by using density functional theory (DFT) and the corresponding experimental structure. See **Supplementary Section S.6.3** for more details. As shown in **Figure 5a**, both the highest occupied crystalline orbital (HOCO) and the lowest unoccupied crystalline orbital (LUCO) are located simultaneously in the organic linker, with a minor contribution of Mn atoms to the first and Ti to the second. The electronic structure of the frontier solid orbitals suggests that the excitons generated in the linker have a low probability of being transferred to the metal node and point instead to a preferential hopping pathway through the π -stacked units for the transport of photogenerated charge carriers.

To test this possibility experimentally, we first used e-beam lithography to attempt single-crystal multi-contact measurements. However, the contacts were systematically lost during the lift-off process after Au evaporation (**Figure S25**) and we opted to deposit freshly made MUV-35 crystals over a Si/SiO₂ (285 nm) substrate by drop casting, to avoid any damage by crystal manipulation, followed by their wire bonding into a chip with silver paint contacts (**Figure 5b**). It should be noted that the colour change of the crystals during their handling was indicative of the formation of the thermodynamically more stable closed structure, thus restricting transport measures to the folded framework only and preventing comparison with other MUV-35 states. We used a Keithley 6517b electrometer to measure I-V curves of the contacted crystals in ambient atmosphere both, in dark, and under irradiation with visible blue light (Kessil PR160L-440 nm lamp). As shown in **Figure 5c**, we observe an increase of 4 orders of magnitude in transport current ($\Delta R = 10^4$), that is perfectly reproducible and stable over time when the crystal is irradiated with ON/OFF cycles (**Figure 5d**).

According to the analysis of the crystals with Focused Ion Beam Scanning Electron Microscope (FIB-SEM) that confirm cross sections of approximately 20 μm (**Figure S29**), this change corresponds to a jump in conductivity (σ) from $\sim 1.7 \times 10^{-7} S \cdot m^{-1}$ to $\sim 2.5 \times 10^{-3} S \cdot m^{-1}$. Other though-transport conductive MOFs based on linker-based redox-active cores comparable to BTT, such as TTF, display intrinsic room temperature electrical conductivities ranging from 10^{-2} to $10^{-8} S \cdot m^{-1}$ depending on the specific type of packing that fixes the distance and relative orientation between the aforementioned units (**Table S8**). These factors serve to control the overlap integral and, subsequently, the mobility of the charge carriers available. The packing of BTT columns in MUV-35-c seems to facilitate transport pathways that are comparable in efficiency to those present in the M_2 (TTFTB) family^[30] with the highest conductivities reported. However, given that this transport pathway would also be operational in the absence of light, the low σ observed suggests a poor density of charge carries when compared with the TTF analogues more prone to oxidation. To confirm this point, we analyzed the photocurrent intensity measured for the same crystal irradiated with lamps at variable wavelengths between 370 and 525 nm. **Figure 5e** shows how the photocurrent scales rapidly in intensity as it approaches the absorption maximum at 440 nm, while it decreases drastically when irradiated with lower energies. The good reproducibility of these results over different crystals confirms a direct relationship between light and the charge carrier's population for MUV-35-c (**Figure S27**).

3. Conclusion

With MUV-35, we have expanded the group of flexible MOFs by integrating titanium frameworks into this category for the first time. Our crystallographic study reveals the mechanism by which this two-fold catenated framework can spontaneously desorb DMF, folding its structure through a conformational

change and rearrangement of the BTTTB linkers. This enables the framework to accommodate solvent loss by modifying its packing to maximize the spatial organization and density of π - π interactions required to stabilize the closed state. This change involves a cell volume compression of approximately 40% which does not affect the crystallinity of the material that maintains a porous structure. Compared to other flexible multistate frameworks with energy minima in close proximity, the folding of the framework is thermodynamically driven and proceeds irreversibly with minimum effect of the guest-framework interactions.

This structural change in MUV-35-c results in the formation of an efficient through-space transport pathway for single-crystal photoconductivities of $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ under visible light for an ON/OFF ratio (ΔR) of four orders of magnitude. While this value is close to the highest conductivities reported for this type of through-space electrical transport in π -stacked conductive MOFs,^[66] in this case it is accompanied by significantly higher porosity of near to $1000 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. Given the growing interest in titanium MOFs for photocatalytic applications, we argue their ability to adapt their structure and provide new electrical transport pathways for charge carrier mobility offers a more molecularly attuned alternative to improve the efficiency of photocatalytic processes than other strategies typically adapted from conventional semiconductors. Furthermore, our results also suggest direct control of the photogenerated current by the wavelength used during irradiation, which could provide a more reproducible and systematic alternative to the use of chemical oxidants to modify the electrical conductivity of the material under light exposure.

4. Experimental Section/Methods

Materials and methods are available in the Supporting Information. CCDC2373154, CCDC2373155 and CCDC2373156 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the H2020 program (ERC-2021-COG-101043428), the Generalitat Valenciana (PROMETEU/2021/054, MFA/2022/026, and SEJI-GENT/2021/059), and the Spanish government (CEX2019-000919-M, PID2020-118117RB-I00, & CNS2022-135677). C.C.-G. and M.G. thank the Spanish government for a FPI grant (PRE2021-098634) and RyC Fellowship (RYC2021-034609-I). N.M.P. thanks La Caixa Foundation for a Postdoctoral Junior Leader–Retaining Fellowship (ID100010434, fellowship code LCF/BQ/PR20/11770014). We also thank the University of Valencia-SCSIE for research facilities, ALBA for the access to synchrotron radiation at the beamlines BL13 XALOC (2023087722) and BSC-RES for computational resources (QHS-2024-2-0029).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

- [1] H. Furukawa, K. E. Cordova, M. O'Keeffe, O. M. Yaghi, *Science* **2013**, *341*, 1230444.
- [2] P. Z. Moghadam, A. Li, S. B. Wiggan, A. Tao, A. G. P. Maloney, P. A. Wood, S. C. Ward, D. Fairen-Jimenez, *Chem. Mater.* **2017**, *29*, 2618.
- [3] C. S. Diercks, M. J. Kalmutzki, N. J. Diercks, O. M. Yaghi, *ACS Cent. Sci.* **2018**, *4*, 1457.
- [4] M. J. Kalmutzki, N. Hanikel, O. M. Yaghi, *Sci. Adv.* **2018**, *4*, eaat9180.
- [5] S. M. Cohen, *Chem. Rev.* **2011**, *112*, 970.
- [6] M. Zhao, K. Yuan, Y. Wang, G. Li, J. Guo, L. Gu, W. Hu, H. Zhao, Z. Tang, *Nature* **2016**, *539*, 76.
- [7] A. Cadiau, K. Adil, P. M. Bhatt, Y. Belmabkhout, M. Eddaoudi, *Science* **2016**, *353*, 137.
- [8] H. Kim, S. Yang, S. R. Rao, S. Narayanan, E. A. Kapustin, H. Furukawa, A. S. Umans, O. M. Yaghi, E. N. Wang, *Science* **2017**, *356*, 430.
- [9] A. Cadiau, Y. Belmabkhout, K. Adil, P. M. Bhatt, R. S. Pillai, A. Shkurenko, C. Martineau-Corcus, G. Maurin, M. Eddaoudi, *Science* **2017**, *356*, 731.
- [10] L. Li, R.-B. Lin, R. Krishna, H. Li, S. Xiang, H. Wu, J. Li, W. Zhou, B. Chen, *Science* **2018**, *362*, 443.
- [11] S. Horike, S. Shimomura, S. Kitagawa, *Nat. Chem.* **2009**, *1*, 695.
- [12] A. Boutin, M. Springuel-Huet, A. Nossov, A. Gédéon, T. Loiseau, C. Volkringer, G. Férey, F. Coudert, A. H. Fuchs, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2009**, *48*, 8314.
- [13] R. Kitaura, K. Seki, G. Akiyama, S. Kitagawa, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2003**, *42*, 428.
- [14] S. Krause, V. Bon, I. Senkovska, U. Stoeck, D. Wallacher, D. M. Töbrens, S. Zander, R. S. Pillai, G. Maurin, F.-X. Coudert, S. Kaskel, *Nature* **2016**, *532*, 348.
- [15] H. Sato, W. Kosaka, R. Matsuda, A. Hori, Y. Hijikata, R. V. Belosludov, S. Sakaki, M. Takata, S. Kitagawa, *Science* **2014**, *343*, 167.
- [16] J. A. Mason, J. Oktawiec, M. K. Taylor, M. R. Hudson, J. Rodriguez, J. E. Bachman, M. I. Gonzalez, A. Cervellino, A. Guagliardi, C. M. Brown, P. L. Llewellyn, N. Masciocchi, J. R. Long, *Nature* **2015**, *527*, 357.
- [17] C. Gu, N. Hosono, J.-J. Zheng, Y. Sato, S. Kusaka, S. Sakaki, S. Kitagawa, *Science* **2019**, *363*, 387.
- [18] N. Yanai, K. Kitayama, Y. Hijikata, H. Sato, R. Matsuda, Y. Kubota, M. Takata, M. Mizuno, T. Uemura, S. Kitagawa, *Nat. Mater.* **2011**, *10*, 787.
- [19] Y. Takashima, V. M. Martínez, S. Furukawa, M. Kondo, S. Shimomura, H. Uehara, M. Nakahama, K. Sugimoto, S. Kitagawa, *Nat. Commun.* **2011**, *2*, 168.
- [20] P. Horcajada, C. Serre, G. Maurin, N. A. Ramsahye, F. Balas, M. Vallet-Regí, M. Sebban, F. Taulelle, G. Férey, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, *130*, 6774.
- [21] G. Skorupskii, K. N. Le, D. L. M. Cordova, L. Yang, T. Chen, C. H. Hendon, M. Q. Arguilla, M. Dincă, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **2022**, *119*, e2205127119.
- [22] K. Fan, J. Li, Y. Xu, C. Fu, Y. Chen, C. Zhang, G. Zhang, J. Ma, T. Zhai, C. Wang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2023**, *145*, 12682.
- [23] C.-L. Chen, C. Wang, X.-Y. Zheng, R. Zhang, Y. Xu, G.-L. Zhuang, L.-S. Long, L.-S. Zheng, X.-J. Kong, Y. Cao, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2023**, *145*, 16983.
- [24] J.-H. Dou, M. Q. Arguilla, Y. Luo, J. Li, W. Zhang, L. Sun, J. L. Mancuso, L. Yang, T. Chen, L. R. Parent, G. Skorupskii, N. J. Libretto, C. Sun, M. C. Yang, P. V. Dip, E. J. Brignole, J. T. Miller, J. Kong, C. H. Hendon, J. Sun, M. Dincă, *Nat. Mater.* **2021**, *20*, 222.
- [25] G. Skorupskii, B. A. Trump, T. W. Kasel, C. M. Brown, C. H. Hendon, M. Dincă, *Nat. Chem.* **2020**, *12*, 131.
- [26] H.-Y. Wang, L. Cui, J.-Z. Xie, C. F. Leong, D. M. D'Alessandro, J.-L. Zuo, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2017**, *345*, 342.
- [27] L. Qu, H. Iguchi, S. Takaishi, F. Habib, C. F. Leong, D. M. D'Alessandro, T. Yoshida, H. Abe, E. Nishibori, M. Yamashita, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141*, 6802.
- [28] J. Y. Koo, Y. Yakiyama, G. R. Lee, J. Lee, H. C. Choi, Y. Morita, M. Kawano, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 1776.
- [29] L. Sun, S. S. Park, D. Sheberla, M. Dinca, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 14772.
- [30] S. S. Park, E. R. Hontz, L. Sun, C. H. Hendon, A. Walsh, T. V. Voorhis, M. Dinca, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 1774.
- [31] L. S. Xie, M. Dincă, *Isr. J. Chem.* **2018**, *58*, 1119.
- [32] L. S. Xie, E. V. Alexandrov, G. Skorupskii, D. M. Proserpio, M. Dincă, *Chem. Sci.* **2019**, *10*, 8558.
- [33] J. Castells-Gil, S. Mañas-Valero, I. J. Vitórica-Yrezábal, D. Ananias, J. Rocha, R. Santiago, S. T. Bromley, J. J. Baldoví, E. Coronado, M. Souto, G. M. Espallargas, *Chem. A Eur. J.* **2019**, *25*, 12636.

- [34] J. Su, T.-H. Hu, R. Murase, H.-Y. Wang, D. M. D'Alessandro, M. Kurmoo, J.-L. Zuo, *Inorg. Chem.* **2019**, *58*, 3698.
- [35] D. Lee, S. Lee, I. Choi, M. Kim, *Smart Mol.* **2024**, *2*, DOI 10.1002/smo.20240002.
- [36] A. Molina-Ontoria, I. Zimmermann, I. Garcia-Benito, P. Gratia, C. Roldán-Carmona, S. Aghazada, M. Graetzel, M. K. Nazeeruddin, N. Martín, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2016**, *55*, 6270.
- [37] B. Lerma-Berlanga, C. R. Ganivet, N. Almora-Barrios, R. Vismara, J. A. R. Navarro, S. Tatay, N. M. Padial, C. Martí-Gastaldo, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2022**, *61*, e202208139.
- [38] J. Castells-Gil, N. M. Padial, N. Almora-Barrios, R. Gil-San-Millán, M. Romero-Ángel, V. Torres, I. da Silva, B. C. J. Vieira, J. C. Waerenborgh, J. Jagiello, J. A. R. Navarro, S. Tatay, C. Martí-Gastaldo, *Chem* **2020**, *6*, 3118.
- [39] N. M. Padial, B. Lerma-Berlanga, N. Almora-Barrios, J. Castells-Gil, I. da Silva, M. de la Mata, S. I. Molina, J. Hernández-Saz, A. E. Platero-Prats, S. Tatay, C. Martí-Gastaldo, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142*, 6638.
- [40] V. Guillermin, D. Maspoch, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141*, 16517.
- [41] J. Kim, B. Chen, T. M. Reineke, H. Li, M. Eddaoudi, D. B. Moler, M. O'Keeffe, O. M. Yaghi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2001**, *123*, 8239.
- [42] B. Bueken, F. Vermoortele, D. E. P. Vanpoucke, H. Reinsch, C. Tsou, P. Valvekens, T. D. Baerdemaeker, R. Ameloot, C. E. A. Kirschhock, V. V. Speybroeck, J. M. Mayer, D. D. Vos, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 13912.
- [43] Q. Yan, J. Wang, L. Zhang, J. Liu, M. Wahiduzzaman, N. Yan, L. Yu, R. Dupuis, H. Wang, G. Maurin, M. Hirscher, P. Guo, S. Wang, J. Du, *Nat. Commun.* **2023**, *14*, 4189.
- [44] D.-F. Lu, Y.-P. Han, Y. Sun, F. Wang, J. Zhang, *Cryst. Growth Des.* **2023**, *23*, 3778.
- [45] G. Férey, C. Serre, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2009**, *38*, 1380.
- [46] A. Schneemann, V. Bon, I. Schwedler, I. Senkovska, S. Kaskel, R. A. Fischer, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2014**, *43*, 6062.
- [47] C. Serre, F. Millange, C. Thouvenot, M. Noguès, G. Marsolier, D. Louër, G. Férey, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2002**, *124*, 13519.
- [48] C. Serre, C. Mellot-Draznieks, S. Surblé, N. Audebrand, Y. Filinchuk, G. Férey, *Science* **2007**, *315*, 1828.
- [49] J. D. Gale, L. M. LeBlanc, P. R. Spackman, A. Silvestri, P. Raiteri, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2021**, *17*, 7827.
- [50] Y.-Y. Liu, S. Couck, M. Vandichel, M. Grzywa, K. Leus, S. Biswas, D. Volkmer, J. Gascon, F. Kapteijn, J. F. M. Denayer, M. Waroquier, V. V. Speybroeck, P. V. D. Voort, *Inorg. Chem.* **2013**, *52*, 113.
- [51] L. Bondorf, J. L. Fiorio, V. Bon, L. Zhang, M. Maliuta, S. Ehrling, I. Senkovska, J. D. Evans, J.-O. Joswig, S. Kaskel, T. Heine, M. Hirscher, *Sci. Adv.* **n.d.**, *8*, eabn7035.
- [52] R. Demuyndt, S. M. J. Rogge, L. Vanduyffhuys, J. Wieme, M. Waroquier, V. V. Speybroeck, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2017**, *13*, 5861.
- [53] F.-X. Coudert, M. Jeffroy, A. H. Fuchs, A. Boutin, C. Mellot-Draznieks, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, *130*, 14294.
- [54] F.-X. Coudert, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, *12*, 10904.
- [55] D. Bousquet, F.-X. Coudert, A. G. J. Fossati, A. V. Neimark, A. H. Fuchs, A. Boutin, *J. Chem. Phys.* **2013**, *138*, 174706.
- [56] A. Boutin, M. Springuel-Huet, A. Nossov, A. Gédéon, T. Loiseau, C. Volkringer, G. Férey, F. Coudert, A. H. Fuchs, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2009**, *48*, 8314.
- [57] I. Senkovska, V. Bon, L. Abylgazina, M. Mendt, J. Berger, G. Kieslich, P. Petkov, J. L. Fiorio, J. Joswig, T. Heine, L. Schaper, C. Bachetzky, R. Schmid, R. A. Fischer, A. Pöpl, E. Brunner, S. Kaskel, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2023**, *62*, e202218076.
- [58] S. Krause, N. Hosono, S. Kitagawa, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59*, 15325.
- [59] S. Horike, S. Shimomura, S. Kitagawa, *Nat. Chem.* **2009**, *1*, 695.
- [60] E. R. Johnson, S. Keinan, P. Mori-Sánchez, J. Contreras-García, A. J. Cohen, W. Yang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132*, 6498.
- [61] M. Alonso, T. Woller, F. J. Martín-Martínez, J. Contreras-García, P. Geerlings, F. D. Proft, *Chem. A Eur. J.* **2014**, *20*, 4931.
- [62] K. Roztocki, F. Formalik, A. Krawczuk, I. Senkovska, B. Kuchta, S. Kaskel, D. Matoga, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59*, 4491.
- [63] C. Martí-Gastaldo, D. Antypov, J. E. Warren, M. E. Briggs, P. A. Chater, P. V. Wiper, G. J. Miller, Y. Z. Khimyak, G. R. Darling, N. G. Berry, M. J. Rosseinsky, *Nat. Chem.* **2014**, *6*, 343.
- [64] A. M. Walker, B. Civaleri, B. Slater, C. Mellot-Draznieks, F. Corà, C. M. Zicovich-Wilson, G. Román-Pérez, J. M. Soler, J. D. Gale, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2010**, *49*, 7501.
- [65] J. Castells-Gil, N. M. Padial, N. Almora-Barrios, J. Albero, A. R. Ruiz-Salvador, J. González-Platas, H. García, C. Martí-Gastaldo, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57*, 8453.
- [66] L. S. Xie, G. Skorupskii, M. Dinca, *Chem. Rev.* **2020**, *120*, 8536.

DISCLAIMER

This document is the unedited Author's version of a Submitted Work that was subsequently accepted for publication in Advance Materials, copyright © WILEY-V C H VERLAG GMBH after peer review.

To access the final edited and published work see: <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202412045>
